

Fabrication and characterization of quercetin-loaded poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/chitosan electrospun mats for use as bioactive wound dressings

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Abstract

Electrospinning technology could be a promising approach for fabricating nanofibrous wound dressings that would facilitate the controlled delivery of biologically active agents. This study involved the preparation of quercetin-loaded poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL)/chitosan (CH) electrospun nanofibers with different quercetin contents, namely 1–10 wt.% quercetin. Characterization of the obtained samples was performed with respect to morphology, physicochemical properties, encapsulation efficiency, *in vitro* drug release behavior, and *in vivo* wound healing activity. The morphology of the materials was evaluated by FE-SEM. XRD and FTIR were used to confirm the incorporation of quercetin into PCL/CH nanofibers. Quercetin addition at moderate concentrations did not adversely affect fiber formation, whereas high concentrations caused significant morphological alterations. XRD and FTIR data revealed effective drug incorporation and amorphous dispersion within the polymer matrix. The entrapment efficiency of quercetin decreased as the amount of drug increased. *In vitro* drug release studies in PBS demonstrated a sustained drug release pattern over the investigated period of 170 h; the release behavior was formulation-dependent. The obtained materials were shown to facilitate the enhancement of wound healing and collagen deposition when tested *in vivo* in comparison with blank PCL scaffolds.

Keywords

Drug-loaded fibers, electrospinning technology, nanofibrous membranes, postsurgical dressing, wound healing

Introduction

The skin is the largest organ in the human body. It is involved in sensation and acts as a barrier against environmental agents, such as chemicals, pathogens, and radiation. Its function is to retain moisture and electrolytes to maintain physiological balance (Walker 2022; Wang et al. 2024). Nonetheless, the integrity of human skin can be affected by mechanical trauma, thermal burns,

chemical injury, or chronic diseases, which can cause lesions and impair the wound-healing process, leading to severe injury and disease (Fard et al. 2025). A wound is defined as the disruption of skin integrity due to certain intrinsic or extrinsic stimuli that cause a change in the structural makeup of tissues. Based on their depth, wounds can be categorized as superficial wounds, where only the epidermis is involved, or full-thickness wounds, where the epidermis and the dermis are involved (Soylu

et al. 2025). Wound healing is a dynamic, complex biological process that involves four overlapping stages: hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling. Although this can naturally preserve tissue integrity, it may be prolonged or incomplete in severe wounds. As such, the development of advanced dressings capable of promoting cell proliferation, maintaining a moist microenvironment, and preventing infection has been recognized as a relevant area of research in biomaterials (Alsaide and Maraie 2023; Zhang et al. 2024).

With the complexity of skin and the requirements of wound healing therapies, much attention has been drawn to more sophisticated techniques that could fabricate an artificial skin extracellular matrix, with electrospinning being a leading technique in this regard. These techniques aim to mimic the natural properties of skin, such as its elasticity and permeability, to enhance healing outcomes. Therefore, in the last decade, electrospinning technology has received considerable attention for the cost-effective and versatile fabrication of nanofibrous scaffolds. High porosity and large surface area-to-volume ratios of nanofibers, with tunable morphology, are attractive features for drug delivery and tissue engineering applications (Oleiwi et al. 2021; Ahmadi Bonakdar and Rodrigue 2024). Nanostructured membranes can be formed by electrospinning, with controlled fiber diameters and pore sizes achieved by modulating parameters such as polymer concentration, viscosity, and applied voltage (Oleiwi et al. 2023).

Among various biopolymers, chitosan (CH) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) are promising materials for wound-healing scaffolds. CH is obtained from chitin and possesses polycationic, hemostatic, and antimicrobial properties, which promote cell proliferation and tissue regeneration (Raina et al. 2026). However, its high viscosity and limited solubility in common solvents severely limit its electrospinnability and mechanical stability in aqueous environments. Blending CH with biodegradable, FDA-approved PCL, which has favorable elasticity and a slow degradation rate, improves the spinnability and durability of the nanofibers under physiological conditions (Fo'ad et al. 2022; Uma Thanu Krishnan Neela et al. 2025).

To further enhance their therapeutic potential, bioactive molecules are incorporated into these nanofibers. Quercetin is one of the most well-known flavonoids because of its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities and is commonly found in fruits and vegetables. In particular, low solubility, rapid metabolism, and light-induced degradation limit its use in clinical applications (Cho et al. 2025; Obead et al. 2025). Attempts have been made to investigate different delivery systems to improve its stability and bioavailability (Hashim et al. 2023). For instance, Arpornmaeklong et al. prepared thermosensitive CH/collagen hydrogels loaded with quercetin for extended release and enhanced antioxidant activity, thereby supporting stem cell growth and tissue regeneration (Arpornmaeklong et al. 2021). Similarly, Viscusi et al. prepared PCL/PVP electrospun membranes loaded with quercetin and achieved controlled release for up to 7 days,

with considerable bioactivity under physiological conditions (Viscusi et al. 2023).

Using a similar approach, Fahimirad et al. reported that PCL/CH/curcumin electrospun membranes achieved optimal wound closure *in vivo* (Fahimirad et al. 2021). Moreover, Pansara et al. showed that CH–silver nanoparticle mats accelerated the contraction and tissue-regeneration phases of wound healing in animal models, highlighting the beneficial synergy between CH and bioactive agents (Pansara et al. 2020).

Previous research has primarily examined quercetin in topical formulations and electrospun membranes, focusing on wound healing and tissue regeneration. The current study focuses on improving quercetin loading in hybrid PCL/CH electrospun nanofibers and evaluates their efficacy as implanted wound-healing mats. This hybrid structure combines hydrophilic CH with hydrophobic PCL to enhance bioactivity and mechanical stability, enabling prolonged local quercetin delivery while maintaining structural integrity. This approach may be beneficial for closed surgical incisions that require controlled drug release and physical support. Despite previous studies on quercetin-loaded hydrogels and surface-applied membranes, limited attention has been given to implanted quercetin-loaded PCL/CH mats in sutured surgical sites, which this study aims to address.

The current study was conducted with the aim of designing and characterizing electrospun nanofibers loaded with quercetin through blending PCL and CH. This research mainly concentrated on the morphological and physicochemical characteristics of the fabricated scaffolds, as well as drug release and bio-spatiotemporal effects. The fabricated hybrid system of PCL and CH was optimized for quercetin delivery, scaffold stability, and tissue regeneration, indicating its application in advanced wound dressings.

Experimental part

Materials

Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) with $M_w = 250,000$ g/mol was sourced from American Polymers Services, Inc. (APS, USA). Chitosan (CH) with $M_w = 1,250,000$ g/mol was purchased from Glentham Life Sciences (UK). Quercetin (QUE $\geq 95\%$; Sigma–Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and Tween 80 were obtained from Central Drug House Ltd. (India) and used. Ethanol (Sigma–Aldrich, $\geq 99.8\%$) of analytical-grade purity was employed. Analytical-grade glacial acetic acid with a purity of approximately 99% was obtained from CARLO ERBA Reagents, Italy.

Membrane preparation

The electrospinning technique was used to manufacture the membranes in this work. A few important steps were performed for membrane manufacture. PCL polymer was first dissolved in glacial acetic acid (99%) solvent, then

Figure 1. Electrospinning steps for the PCL/CH membrane.

stirred for 4 h at 500 rpm and room temperature until a homogeneous polymeric solution with a constant concentration of 12 wt.% was formed. In the same line, CH polymer was dissolved in aqueous acetic acid (70%) solvent, then stirred for 2 h at 500 rpm and room temperature to form a homogeneous polymeric solution with a constant concentration of 1 wt.%.

These mixtures were prepared individually, then combined by adding the CH polymer solution to the PCL polymer solution at a volume ratio of 2:8 (CH:PCL). After 1 h, the mixture was stirred at room temperature to form a uniform blend. Then, 1, 3, 5, and 10 wt.% quercetin relative to the polymer weight, with 0.8% Tween 80, were added to the blend solution. Quercetin was mixed into the blend by stirring overnight. The blend was sonicated using a sonicating homogenizer (Model: 300VT, USA) for 3 min. An electrospinning machine (Bio-electrospinning/Electrospray System ESB-200, South Korea) was used to produce electrospun fibers from the solution. Electrospinning solutions were loaded into a 10 mL syringe fitted with a stainless-steel needle (22 gauge). Polymeric solutions were injected into an electrospinning electrical field via a syringe pump at a constant feed rate of 1 mL/h throughout the process. The collector was set at approximately 18 cm from the syringe needle. A high-voltage supply of approximately 20 kV was applied between the syringe needle and the collector. Electrospinning was also carried out for 2 h to prepare the membranes, as shown in Fig. 1.

Characterization

Characterization of the prepared nanofiber membranes was performed using a combination of morphological, structural, thermal, chemical, and release analysis techniques.

Morphological analysis was carried out using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Zeiss, Germany). Images were taken to analyze the surface

structure, fiber continuity, diameter distribution, pore size, and porosity. This analysis helped evaluate the uniformity of the electrospun fibers and detect any bead formation or surface irregularities.

Crystalline structure testing was performed for the samples via X-ray diffraction (XRD; Philips PW1730, Netherlands). Diffractograms were obtained by applying Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV and 40 mA at a 2θ range of 3° to 32° . The obtained patterns were used to characterize the crystallinity of pure polymers and drug-loaded nanofibers, and the differences in crystallinity were attributed to both molecular interactions and drug amorphization.

Thermal measurements were carried out by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on a TA Instruments Q600 (USA). Each sample, approximately 5 mg, was packed in aluminum pans and heated from 20°C to 500°C at $10^\circ \text{C}/\text{min}$ with nitrogen flow of 60 mL/min. The DSC thermograms were evaluated for areas indicating melting transitions, change in the glass transition temperature, and changes reflecting polymer–drug compatibility or decreased crystallinity.

Using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR; Bruker Tensor 27, Germany), chemical interactions were determined and functional groups were confirmed. Composite nanofibers were then analyzed to correlate the spectra with those of various components and detect characteristic peaks and shifts as evidence of hydrogen bonding or chemical interactions between PCL, CH, and quercetin.

Drug entrapment efficiency of nanofibers loaded with quercetin was determined by dissolving 10 mg of nanofibers in 0.5 mL of glacial acetic acid, and the resulting solution was further diluted using ethanol to dissolve the quercetin. The resulting solution was centrifuged at a speed of 2000 rpm for 15 min to separate the polymer pellet. The supernatant liquid was filtered, and the resulting solution was analyzed using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 373 nm. The concentration of quercetin

in the solution was analyzed from the calibration curve prepared using ethanol solutions. The entrapment efficiency was calculated using Equation (1).

$$EE(\%) = \frac{\text{Amount of quercetin present in NFs}}{\text{theoretical amount of quercetin in NFs}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The *in vitro* release experiment of quercetin-loaded fibers was performed using 25 mL of phosphate buffer solution (PBS), pH 7.4, containing 1% Tween 80, at 37 °C for 170 h. At each predefined time interval, 2 mL of sample solution was withdrawn, and an equal volume of fresh medium containing 1% Tween 80 was added. The cumulative drug release (%) was calculated based on the exact amount of quercetin released from the prepared nanofibers, which was determined by entrapment efficiency (EE) analysis. Lu et al. concluded that the addition of surfactants, particularly 1% Tween 80, increases the solubility of quercetin (Lu et al. 2019). The experiment was performed in triplicate, and the findings are expressed as mean \pm SD.

The wettability of quercetin-loaded electrospun PCL/CH mats at various drug concentrations and the as-prepared membranes was assessed using a contact angle device (Type: CAM 110, Germany). During this inspection, water was placed in a syringe, automatically dispensed onto the membrane surface, and the equipment evaluated

the acquired image to determine the contact angle in approximately 3 s.

Statistical analysis of all experiments was conducted in triplicate to ensure result reliability, with data expressed as mean \pm SD. Histological evaluation via H&E staining employed a semi-quantitative scoring system, with treatment effects and healing time analyzed through two-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc test, also with $p < 0.05$ for significance.

***In vivo* experimental procedure**

In this study, 27 healthy Wistar rats with an average weight of 250 ± 20 g were used. The animals were individually housed in wire cages under standard laboratory conditions with unrestricted access to a standard diet and water, and they were acclimated for 15 days before the experiment. The rats were randomly divided into three equal groups ($n = 9$), and a full-thickness linear surgical wound of 4 cm was created on the dorsal area of each animal, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Group A served as the untreated control group. Meanwhile, a PCL/CH polymer mat was implanted in group B. In group C, a PCL/CH mat loaded with quercetin was implanted. Before the surgical procedure, the animals were fasted for 2 h and then anesthetized us-

Figure 2. *In vivo* surgical procedure for wound creation and mat implantation, including (A) rat preparation, (B) creation of a full-thickness wound, (C) placement of the electrospun mat, and (D) wound closure using sutures.

Figure 3. FE-SEM image of the electrospun PCL/CH blend membrane.

ing ketamine hydrochloride (75 mg/kg) and xylazine hydrochloride (10 mg/kg) via intraperitoneal injection. The dorsal hair was shaved over an 8 cm area along the midline, and the surgical site was disinfected sequentially with chlorhexidine gluconate, 70% isopropanol, and 1.5% iodine tincture, with all procedures carried out under strict aseptic conditions and the animals in a ventral recumbent position.

Skin biopsy samples were collected from three animals in each group on days 7, 14, and 21. They were fixed and processed histologically for pathological evaluation, including assessment of the inflammatory response, re-epithelialization, collagen deposition, and overall wound-healing progress.

Histological examination was performed on granulation tissues that were fixed in formalin, embedded in paraffin, cut into 5 mm-thick sections, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Under an optical microscope, histological alterations were qualitatively identified. All experiments involving animals were carried out according to the standard practice for the care and handling of laboratory animals. These experiments were ethically approved by the institutional research ethics committee (Approval No. 57). All Wistar rats employed in the experiment were obtained from the animal house of our institution. Every effort was made to minimize animal distress.

Results and discussion

Morphology of the electrospun fibers

Surface morphology of the electrospun PCL/CH blend fibers is shown in Fig. 3. As observed, the as-spun fibers exhibited a bead-on-string structure. This may be linked to the low considered polymer concentration. Thus, incomplete entanglement of the polymer chains led to the disruption of the solution components, resulting in the formation of droplets rather than fibers during the electrospinning process (Olewi et al. 2025). The fiber diameter distribution histogram of the blend fibers is displayed in Fig. 3. As is apparent, the electrospun membrane contains fibers with an average diameter of 103.8 nm. The as-spun fibers were selected for the fabrication of drug-loaded electrospun fibers due to several advantages, including high surface area, thin fiber diameter, high porosity, and a simple spinning process.

Fig. 4 shows the variation in the morphology of the quercetin-loaded electrospun PCL/CH nanofibrous mat. Unloaded PCL/CH nanofibers had an average fiber diameter of 103 ± 5 nm. Loading the PCL/CH nanofibers with quercetin led to a progressive increase in the diameter of the fibers, and the fiber diameter reached 161 ± 9 nm for 10% loading of quercetin. Fiber bead formation was observed in samples loaded with 1% quercetin due to

Figure 4. FE-SEM images of the PCL/CH blend membranes loaded with various concentrations of quercetin, including (A) 1, (B) 3, (C) 5, and (D) 10 wt.%.

the instability of the electrospinning process. Conversely, loading the PCL/CH nanofibers with 3% and 5% quercetin improved the homogeneity of fiber morphology. Specifically, samples with 5% loading demonstrated superior fiber structure, being characterized by fewer defects. For loading above 10%, fiber diameters increased due to crystalline aggregates and deposits on the surface of the fibers. Overall, the results reveal that quercetin content greatly influences fiber morphology by changing the characteristics of the spinning solution (dos Santos et al. 2018).

Additionally, Fig. 5 shows that the variation in drug concentration in the polymeric solution directly affected the morphology and diameter of the electrospun fibers. As the drug concentration increased, the solution viscosity increased, while its electrical conductivity decreased, thereby reducing the stretching force acting on the electrospinning jet. Consequently, the reduced tension of the

jet resulted in fibers with greater average diameters. At excessive concentrations, drug molecules also precipitated on the fiber surface and were not fully incorporated into the matrix, leading to surface particle formation and loss of structural uniformity in the SEM images (Wang and Wang 2021; Munawar et al. 2025). Consequently, these results indicate that the ideal drug concentration for the same blend was 5% quercetin, as uniform fiber quality and structural stability can be observed. At higher concentrations, such as 10% quercetin, there is a disruption in the regularity of the fibers, which negatively impacts subsequent drug-release behavior (Stoyanova et al. 2025a).

The changes in the mean pore size of the electrospun membranes, which decreased with increasing quercetin concentration up to 5% and then slightly increased at 10%, were evident in Fig. 5. In any wound dressing, pore size is one of the main factors that control cell migration, fluid

Figure 5. Effect of quercetin concentration on fiber diameter and pore size of electrospun PCL/CH membranes.

permeability, gas exchange, and bacterial penetration. Therefore, its adjustment at the nanoscale is required to provide an optimal environment for wound healing (Mukasheva et al. 2024). On the other hand, porosity plays an important role in controlling the passage of gases, nutrients, and fluids through the membrane, in the release of medication from the membrane, and in maintaining cell adhesion and proliferation at the wound site. It has been documented that the optimal value for wound dressing porosity lies between 60 and 90% (Ortiz-Marqués et al. 2025), as measured using ImageJ software for FE-SEM images; therefore, these results confirm that all prepared membranes in this work showed porosity values within this range and supported their functional efficiency.

X-ray diffraction

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the electrospun PCL/CH blend fibers is shown in Fig. 6. XRD analysis of individual materials and composite nanofibers provides important insights into structural transformations after quercetin incorporation. Pure quercetin exhibits a highly crystalline structure, as reflected by sharp Bragg diffraction peaks at approximately 11° , 13° , 14° , and 28° (Stoyanova et al. 2025b). As expected, poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), as a semicrystalline biodegradable polyester, shows two main Bragg diffraction peaks centered at $2\theta \approx 22^\circ$ and 24° , corresponding to the (110) and (200) planes of its orthorhombic crystal phase (Feng et al. 2023). CH shows an XRD pattern that is distinct from both materials, with a broad hump between 20° and 30° , indicating that CH is mainly in an amorphous state (Mahmoud et al. 2023). On the contrary, when quercetin is embedded within the PCL nanofibers via supercritical CO_2 processing, the XRD patterns present only the characteristics of PCL, whereas the distinctive peaks of crystalline quercetin completely disappear. This indicates that quercetin loses its crystalline structure and becomes molecularly dispersed in an amorphous form within the polymer matrix (García-Casas et al. 2019).

Figure 6. XRD pattern of quercetin only and PCL/CH blend membranes loaded with 0, 3, 5, and 10 wt.% concentrations of quercetin.

Furthermore, an evident decrease in the intensity of PCL peaks was observed with an increase in quercetin concentration. These observations are supported by literature reports confirming that a polymer blend containing less than 20 wt.% quercetin can retain the drug in a fully amorphous state through strong intermolecular interactions with the polymer chains, thereby inhibiting recrystallization (Sanchez-Rexach et al. 2019).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The FTIR spectrum of the blend nanofibrous mat is displayed in Fig. 7. According to the obtained spectra, FTIR analysis was conducted on PCL/CH nanofibers loaded with various concentrations of quercetin to identify the functional groups present and confirm the successful incorporation of the drug into the polymeric matrix. The PCL-CH blend spectrum showed the characteristic absorption bands of PCL at 2927 and 2865 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric and symmetric CH_2 stretching, respectively, whereas the distinct ester carbonyl peak ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching) was observed at 1722 cm^{-1} . Further, CH contributed a broad band in the 3400 – 3200 cm^{-1} region owing to the overlap of O–H and N–H stretching vibrations, along with amide I and amide II bands at approximately 1654 and 1599 cm^{-1} , respectively. Peaks in the range of 1152 – 1031 cm^{-1} , particularly at 1105 and 1045 cm^{-1} , were assigned to the stretching of C–O–C and C–O groups in the saccharide structure, confirming the presence of chitosan (Hashemi et al. 2023; Işık and Teke 2025).

Pure quercetin exhibited a broad peak near 3400 cm^{-1} due to phenolic O–H groups, a strong $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching of the aromatic ketone at approximately 1654 cm^{-1} , aromatic C=C stretching at approximately 1599 and 1514 cm^{-1} , and phenolic C–O stretching near 1240 cm^{-1} . In the case of quercetin-loaded nanofibers, the gradual increase in the intensity of the aromatic C=C peaks at approximately 1599 and 1514 cm^{-1} with increasing drug concentration confirmed the incorporation of quercetin into the matrix (Wangsawangrungrung et al. 2022).

Figure 7. FTIR spectra of quercetin only and PCL/CH blend membranes loaded with 0, 3, 5, and 10 wt.% concentrations of quercetin.

Furthermore, a broad O–H/N–H stretching band at approximately 3340 cm^{-1} increased in intensity and slightly shifted due to the hydrogen-bonding effect of the hydroxyl groups of quercetin with the amino and hydroxyl groups of CH. The presence of functional group peaks indicates that neither quercetin nor the polymer components underwent chemical degradation during electrospinning. These results confirm that quercetin is chemically compatible with the PCL/CH matrix, making it suitable for electrospun membranes for wound healing (Eskitoros-Togay et al. 2018).

Differential scanning calorimetry analysis

The DSC analysis of the blend nanofibrous mat is shown in Fig. 8. Pure quercetin exhibited a well-defined, sharp endothermic peak at approximately $320\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponding to its crystalline melting point, followed by another exothermic peak at approximately $388\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ associated with thermal degradation (Anjani et al. 2025). In the case of the PCL/CH/quercetin mat, only the melting peak of PCL was observed at approximately $62\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the characteristic melting peak of quercetin at $320\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ completely disappeared. The absence of such a peak establishes that quercetin did not exist in crystalline form and was dispersed within the polymer blend in an amorphous form (Sehrawat et al. 2023). The findings from DSC analysis indicate that quercetin has been incorporated within the PCL/CH blend system and is in an amorphous state, as illustrated in Fig. 8.

Wettability

Fig. 9 illustrates the effect of quercetin concentration on the water contact angle of electrospun PCL/CH membranes, with values presented as bars accompanied by the standard error.

There is a gradual decrease in water contact angle from 92.4° for the neat blend (PCL/CH) to 78.1° at 10% querce-

Figure 8. DSC thermograms of pure quercetin and the PCL/CH/5% quercetin electrospun membrane.

Figure 9. Contact angle for PCL/CH blend membranes loaded with different quercetin concentrations.

tin loading, confirming an enhancement in surface hydrophilicity (Viscusi et al. 2023). Lower drug concentrations (1–5%) produced a mild reduction due to limited exposure of quercetin on the fiber surface, whereas the significant drop at 10% indicates surface enrichment of polar phenolic groups ($-\text{OH}$), which is consistent with previous reports on flavonoid-loaded PCL systems (Augustine et al. 2019).

Drug entrapment efficiency

When considering the drug's total miscibility with the polymer, its non-volatile nature, and its optimal concentration, the entrapment efficiency of a nanofiber mat should be nearly 100%. At higher drug concentrations, the encapsulation efficiency decreases, most likely due to the loss of excess drug as aggregates on the nanofiber surface that escape encapsulation into the nanofibers. Fibrous materials, except those containing 10% quercetin, displayed good entrapment efficiency, as shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Encapsulation efficiency of quercetin-loaded electrospun PCL/CH mats at different drug concentrations.

Drug *in vitro* release profile

The release behavior of quercetin from electrospun PCL/CH membranes was evaluated using the kinetic models zero-order (Equation (2)), first-order (Equation (3)), Higuchi (Equation (4)), and Korsmeyer–Peppas (Equation (5)), in which the fraction of released drug, Q , is related to time by the model-specific constant, k (Eskitoros-Togay et al. 2018; Viscusi et al. 2023). As illustrated in Table 1, the release profiles exhibit a two-phase pattern: an initial burst release, followed by a slower, sustained stage until a plateau is reached. The rapid first stage is attributed to the immediate dissolution of quercetin molecules on or near the fiber surface upon exposure to the release medium. The subsequent slower phase takes over as the membrane starts swelling, the fibers become denser, the pore channels shrink, and diffusion becomes restricted (Karuppappan et al. 2022).

$$Q = K_0 \times t \quad (2)$$

$$\ln(Q_0 - Q_t) = \ln Q_0 - K_1 t \quad (3)$$

$$Q = K_H \times t^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

$$Q = K_R \times t^n \quad (5)$$

where Q denotes the total drug fraction released up to time t , and k is the kinetic constant of each model.

This release behavior depends on the polymer composition. PCL is hydrophobic and thus restricts water penetration and reduces drug mobility, whereas CH is hydrophilic, absorbing water, swelling, and providing additional internal pathways for diffusion. Quercetin contains hydrophilic hydroxyl groups and hydrophobic aromatic rings; therefore, its distribution relies on the polarity of the surrounding matrix. It tends to aggregate in domains rich in PCL, whereas regions rich in CH enhance miscibility and promote diffusion (Paolella et al. 2024).

Table 1. Parameters of the kinetics model.

Formula	Zero R^2	First R^2	Higuchi R^2	Korsmeyer n ($\leq 60\%$)	Korsmeyer R^2 ($\leq 60\%$)
B1	0.7088	0.8405	0.9102	0.7384	0.9705
B3	0.6044	0.7664	0.7994	0.7441	0.9937
B5	0.5563	0.7273	0.7571	0.7625	0.9973

However, the total quercetin release from the PCL/CH mats produced via electrospinning depended considerably on the amount of quercetin in the sample and its fiber morphology, as demonstrated in Fig. 11. Among the investigated samples, the total quercetin release was the lowest (75%) from the sample containing 1 wt.% quercetin in the mat structure. Such a phenomenon is related to the formation of beads in the fiber structure and fiber morphology irregularities that would hamper the uniformity of drug release into the medium. In turn, for the mats with contents of 3 wt.% and 5 wt.% quercetin in their structure, the values of quercetin release increased to 82.5% and 85%, respectively. This improvement in the release profile was connected with the better uniformity of fiber morphology obtained at higher quercetin concentrations in the samples' structures. The release of quercetin was additionally enhanced due to the hydrophilic nature of CH, facilitating water uptake and, thus, matrix swelling, while the hydrophobic properties of PCL decreased such a process.

According to the kinetic study, the Korsmeyer–Peppas model gave the best fit for the experimental data, with correlation coefficient (R^2) values of 0.9705, 0.9937, and 0.9973 for B1, B3, and B5, respectively. The respective values of the release exponent (n) were found to be 0.7384, 0.7441, and 0.7625. Since all values of n were higher than 0.5, the mode of drug release was classified as non-Fickian, signifying that quercetin release is controlled by diffusion, matrix swelling, and polymer relaxation.

Figure 11. Quercetin release profile from blend electrospun membranes. Data are reported as mean \pm SD from data obtained in three independent experiments.

Figure 12. Macroscopic images showing wound healing progression for three groups: untreated control (a, b, c), PCL/CH electrospun mats (d, e, f), and quercetin-loaded PCL/CH mats (g, h, i) at days 7, 14, and 21, respectively, after surgery.

Histological findings

Electrospun quercetin-loaded PCL/CH mats offer satisfactory mechanical strength with biodegradability and high antioxidant/antibacterial properties, making them suitable for wound dressing and packaging materials, as illustrated in Fig. 12, which represents the macroscopic wound healing progression for the untreated control group and wounds treated with PCL/CH and quercetin-loaded PCL/CH mats on days 7, 14, and 21 post-surgery. Then, research related to H&E in this group involves considerations related to methods to visualize each tissue detail accurately, which would be crucial to identify the histological aspects of wound healing or biocompatibility of quercetin-PCL-CH scaffolds.

Microscopic examination performed on the seventh day for the three groups after treatment revealed substantial variation in tissue response among the studied groups, as shown in Fig. 12a, d, g. The wounds covered with the quercetin-incorporated PCL/CH electrospun membrane displayed the most favorable early regenerative activity. The wound bed was covered with well-organized and vascularized granulation tissue, with initial but compact collagen fiber formation and a marked decrease in inflammatory cell density. These findings indicate early resolution of the inflammatory phase and early tissue reconstruction onset. In contrast, the polymer-only membrane group response was delayed, with evident edema, dissemination of inflammatory cells, and poorly ordered granulation tissue. Collagen fibers were observed to be thin and poorly organized, consistent with and indicative of a continuing intermediate stage of healing. The untreated control group, under these conditions, displayed significant necrosis and progressive tissue degeneration, severe disruption of the usual archi-

ture, and an almost complete lack of mature granulation tissue, illustrating pronounced impairment in early healing.

After 14 days, wound healing progression between the experimental groups became more obvious, as illustrated in Fig. 12b, e, h. Quercetin-treated wounds showed absolute epithelial continuity throughout the wound surface, in addition to dense, tightly packed collagen bundles of thick tissue in the dermis and infrequent inflammatory cells. This evidence confirms a rapidly accelerated progression through the proliferative phase and early scar formation. For the polymer-only group, epithelial regeneration was incomplete or irregular, and modest inflammatory infiltration remained. Collagen deposition was increased, but fibers were still loosely packed and irregular. Small epithelial discontinuities and cyst-like structures were found in many specimens, suggesting delayed stabilization of the tissue. In contrast, the control wounds remained fairly unhealed, with the remaining slough and necrotic debris still coating the wound surface and inhibiting epithelial migration. The high percentage of inflammatory cells indicated chronic inflammation and inhibited the healing process.

On day 21, as reported in Fig. 12c, f, i, the quercetin-loaded electrospun dressing group showed almost complete skin structural restoration. The epidermis had completely restored, and the dermis showed thick, mature, and directed collagen fibers with relatively little residual inflammation, confirming entry into the remodeling process with stable scar development. The polymer-only group experienced prominent but partial recovery. Re-epithelialization was noted, but uneven patterns and residual epithelial clefts and cystic spaces remained. Collagen fibers showed moderate maturation but were less compact and less organized than those in the quercetin-treated group. The control group continued to exhibit severe

Figure 13. Semi-quantitative histological scoring of (a) inflammatory, (b) collagen, and (c) re-epithelialization scores for control, PCL/CH, and PCL/CH/5% Q at 7, 14, and 21 days after surgery. The data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with post-test analysis using the Tukey range test was employed for statistical analysis. The different capital letters demonstrate the statistical difference in values at similar time-point intervals ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Comparative histological evaluation of wound healing among studied groups.

Day	Control	PCL/CH	PCL/CH/5% quercetin
7	Necrosis with poor granulation	Moderate inflammation, immature collagen	Better organized granulation, fewer inflammatory cells
14	Necrotic debris, chronic inflammation	Partial re-epithelialization, moderate inflammation	Full re-epithelialization, dense collagen
21	Persistent necrosis, no remodeling	incomplete closure, cysts, moderate inflammation	Mature scar, complete epithelial closure

healing deficiency, characterized by widespread necrosis, intense inflammatory cell infiltration, and poor collagen remodeling. Large areas of the wound surface remained open or covered by slough, confirming the failure to reach the remodeling stage (Mi et al. 2022; Huang et al. 2024).

Table 2 represents a qualitative summary of the histological observations in the different experimental groups for each healing time point. These qualitative observations agree with the semi-quantitative histological scores as depicted in Fig. 13, indicating that quercetin-loaded PCL/CH resulted in significantly enhanced resolution of inflammation, collagen deposition, and re-epithelialization in contrast with the polymer-only and control groups ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

This work showed that CH and quercetin, when combined with PCL, can yield nanofibrous membranes suitable for postsurgical wound dressing applications. The 3–5 wt.% quercetin membranes displayed a more homogeneous fiber structure and an even distribution of the drug throughout the polymer matrix. Analytical characterizations showed that quercetin was in an amorphous state and well entrapped, with no evidence of degradation. In addition, a gradual, controlled release of the drug has been demonstrated in the release study, favoring healing. Collectively, these characterizations suggest that the PCL/CH–quercetin developed can provide functional wound dressing materials capable of providing passive structural support as well as active, sustained therapeutic action at the tissue level. Overall, the quercetin-loaded PCL/CH mats significantly promoted wound healing by facilitating organized granula-

tion tissue formation, hastening re-epithelialization, and inducing dense collagen deposition, leading to full epithelial closure and mature scar formation by day 21, in contrast to the delayed and incomplete healing observed in the control and polymer-only groups.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: All animal experimental procedures were conducted in strict accordance with the guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the Mustansiriyah University, College of Pharmacy, Iraq, with Approval No. 57. Every effort was made to minimize animal suffering and to use the minimum number of animals necessary to achieve statistically reliable results.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Asmaa A. Oleiwi conceived and designed the study, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and drafted the manuscript. Ghaidaa S. Hameed supervised the research, contributed to data interpretation, critically revised the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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